

Optimal Sizing and Scheduling of DG and V2G with Demand Response in Smart Grids Using Innovative Optimizers

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Abstract

The rapid proliferation of distributed generation (DG) and electric vehicle (EV) in modern power systems has introduced both opportunities and challenges. Efficiently scaling DG and vehicle-to-grid (V2G) aggregators are critical to ensuring reliable and economical network operation. Also, demand response (DR) programs in a smart grid enable the grid operator to communicate with customers to regulate their demand along with supply conditions or pricing signals. When this grid is coupled with the DGs and EVs, DR can be more efficient, as EVs and DGs can respond dynamically to grid needs. Therefore, this research aims to develop innovative strategies for optimizing the integration of DG, DR and EVs aggregators into distribution systems. Key objectives include improving energy cost savings and ensuring efficient real-time optimal scheduling of resources to support sustainable energy management. The study employs three advanced optimization algorithms of educational competition optimizer (ECO), parrot optimizer (PO), and artemisinin optimization (AO) compared with recognized particle swarm optimization (PSO) to model and analyze the integration of DGs and EVs aggregators to minimize the overall operation costs and address both system and components constraints. The study was performed on transmission networks IEEE 24-bus. The results demonstrate that the proposed daily coordinated scheduling of DG, DR, and V2G units effectively minimize operational costs under generation, demand, and units' limits constraints. Among the tested algorithms, AO, PO, and ECO yields the lowest cost compared to PSO.

Keywords

Artemisinin optimization (AO); demand response (DR); educational competition optimizer (ECO); electric vehicles (EVs); optimal scheduling; parrot optimizer (PO); vehicle-to-grid (V2G).

1. Introduction

1.1 Background

The integration of resilient distributed generation (DG) aggregators into modern power distribution systems has seen substantial growth in recent years. The increasing adoption of vehicle-to-grid (V2G) aggregators has further emphasized the critical role of demand response (DR) in optimizing demand-side energy resources since traditional distributed generators have limitations [1]. Advances in smart grid communication technologies have enabled more efficient DR frameworks, allowing for real-time adjustments in electricity consumption patterns [2]. DR end-users and electric vehicle (EV) owners are regarded as customers for the purpose of this definition. It is anticipated that these users will have an efficient impact on the power grid. They can reduce overall operating costs and increase the reliability of

the system in the future by voluntarily managing load demands and DR [3]. However, several challenges impede the optimal implementation of V2G systems, including (i) Nonlinear Optimization Challenges as Traditional optimization methods struggle to guarantee global minimum in multi-energy systems. (ii) Intermittency of Renewable Energy Sources because the unpredictable nature of solar and wind generation complicates grid stability. (iii) Future smart grid concepts and validations are needed to address the increasing complexity of energy demand, exacerbated by load variations like V2G and DR. (iv) V2Gs established random day-ahead scheduling at the parking lot with varying energy costs, charger capacities, and charging/discharging rules. To address these challenges, this study introduces a novel day-ahead scheduling framework aimed at minimizing operational costs while maintaining consumer satisfaction.

DR can be modelled using an elasticity matrix of electricity costs based on load demands [4,5]. Several studies [6-11] found that DR has a considerable strong impact on energy market pricing, reliability, and spinning reserves when using a constant elasticity matrix throughout a specific period. However, the approaches offered limit the effectiveness of EVs due to the assumption of fixed elasticity of specific variables over time. The integration of EVs onto the grid has made DR scheduling challenging because of a lack of information on demand patterns. To increase confidence, DR program operators ask the end user for information [12]. Demand resources need preliminary data from the customer in order to successfully engage in the DR program. Recent studies have explored various the importance of DR optimization techniques and optimal scheduling of DR with cooperation with other generation resources [13-17].

In addition, the increasing penetration of EVs into power grids has spurred research into V2G coordination strategies. Studies demonstrate that well-managed V2G systems can provide substantial economic benefits. Additionally, V2G has been leveraged for emission reduction in microgrids and optimal EV charging management [18-20]. There are some researchers examining optimal EVs charge management and achieved similar results [21,22]. According to the study [23], regression algorithms require training, and their accuracy is influenced by the amount of available data. DR was not included in V2G research investigations, according to the analysis of several papers as [24-31]. This motivates the current study's authors to create the best daily scheduling for DGs, V2Gs and DRs, which is uncommon in the literature.

1.2 Related works

Extensive research has been conducted in recent years addressing the optimal scheduling of distributed generation resources, demand response (DR), and electric vehicles (EVs) in modern smart grid systems. Previous research has focused on optimizing distributed generation (DG), demand response (DR), and electric vehicle (EV) scheduling to minimize operational costs in smart grids in addition, some Studies have been conducted in microgrids and standard test systems like Microgrid, IEEE 33-bus and IEEE 24-bus networks to validate scheduling models. These systems integrate renewable energy sources, DR strategies, and EV charging coordination to assess performance. The use of such benchmarks ensures realistic evaluations of cost and emission reduction strategies in smart grid environments.

The related literature encompasses a diverse set of optimization strategies aimed at enhancing operational efficiency, renewable energy integration, DR participation, and EV coordination across different power system contexts. Study [32] employed a GAMS-based formulation to reduce operating costs and increase renewable utilization in microgrids, highlighting the benefits of BESS integration while noting the absence of real-time data and advanced computational techniques. A MILP framework in [33]

targeted reductions in imported fuel and overall grid operational costs, achieving high self-consumption and measurable V2G utilization, though important technical factors such as battery degradation and AC power flow were not incorporated. The two-stage stochastic and Modified Firefly Algorithm approach in [34] demonstrated significant improvements in voltage regulation and operational cost minimization within an IEEE 33-bus distribution system, despite omitting transmission-level considerations. A combination of PSO variants and machine-learning methods in [7] focused on cost minimization but lacked detailed representation of distribution network characteristics. The sequence operation theory and linearization techniques applied in [35] improved user satisfaction and reduced costs within a Chinese energy system; however, the study assumed ideal demand response participation, excluded EV flexibility, and overlooked battery degradation. A heuristic greedy method in [36] yielded notable cost savings in hybrid microgrids yet remained constrained by limited DR integration and short-sighted decision-making. Study [37] introduced a multi-agent MACD strategy for EV charging and discharging, achieving cost reductions for EV owners, though simplifications in behavioral modeling and tariff structures limited its realism. The Walrus Optimization Algorithm in [38] enhanced power quality and reduced losses through optimal DG allocation across IEEE and real-world systems but did not address comprehensive multi-resource integration. Deep Q-learning in [39] provided effective charge/discharge coordination in microgrids, though without detailed consideration of demand response time-slot dynamics. A column-and-constraint generation approach supported by MILP in [40] achieved multi-objective operational cost reductions but lacked sophisticated uncertainty modeling related to weather and market conditions. Finally, the NSGA-II-based framework in [41] successfully balanced cost minimization and environmental enhancement in a multi-regional energy system, despite uncertainties associated with user participation in demand response programs. High renewable penetration increases the need for flexible and well-optimized distribution networks. Prior work has shown the importance of grid flexibility [42], optimized DG placement for improved performance [43], and probabilistic hosting capacity assessment under non-sinusoidal conditions [44]. These studies highlight the need for advanced optimization to support reliable renewable integration.

While several studies have explored individual aspects of DG, DR, and V2G integration, their combined impact on smart grid operations remains largely underexplored. To address this gap, the present study proposes a comprehensive daily scheduling strategy for V2G/DR aggregators. The main objective is to develop a coordinated, hourly optimization framework for scheduling distributed generators and electric vehicle energy storage systems within smart distribution networks under DR participation. Unlike conventional approaches, the proposed model enables interactive consumers to actively participate in grid operations, improving flexibility and responsiveness. By including an advanced optimizers, the study enhances operational cost efficiency, system resilience, and equitable energy resource allocation while considering grid constraints.

1.3 Contributions

This study aims to develop innovative strategy for optimizing the integration of DG, DR and EVs aggregators into distribution systems for improving energy cost savings and ensuring efficient real-time optimal scheduling of resources. Major contributions in this paper are:

- Develop innovative strategies for optimizing the integration of DG, DR and EVs aggregators into distribution systems.

- Propose optimal sizing and scheduling of DG and V2G with DR units using advanced optimizers to enhance system performance and minimize system total operational costs while considering all system constraints.
- Employs three advanced optimization algorithms: ECO, PO, and AO.
- Validation of the developed optimizers is demonstrated by compared with recognized conventional particle swarm optimization (PSO).
- Demonstrates the effectiveness of the proposed strategy through comprehensive simulations performed on transmission network (IEEE 24-bus system).
- Improving energy cost savings and ensuring efficient real-time optimal scheduling of resources to support sustainable energy management.

1.4 Organization

This manuscript's remaining sections are arranged as follows. Sections 2 introduce the problem description and formulation. Section 3 shows the utilized optimization algorithms. While Section 4 offers case study data. Section 5 presents the findings of the simulation. Lastly, Sections 6 give the and conclusions and recommendations for future work.

2. Problem Formulation

The increasing penetration of EVs, DG, and DR programs introduces both opportunities and challenges for modern power systems [7, 45]. While these technologies enhance grid flexibility, reduce carbon emissions, and lower operational costs, their unpredictable nature and complex interactions make optimal scheduling a critical yet challenging task [46].

This research investigates the day-ahead and real-time optimal scheduling problem for a distribution network with EV fleets (with V2G capability), diesel-based DG, incentive-based DR programs, and dynamic electricity pricing. The goal is to develop an optimal scheduling frame for EVs, DR, and DG. The optimization process aims to minimize the fitness function for the total operational costs (e.g., energy procurement, and DG fuel costs), and improve user satisfaction through EV charging convenience and DR incentive-based participation using load shifting and curtailment tools. The core methodology of optimal scheduling is given in the main flowchart on Fig. 1. In this flowchart, the step-by-step calculation of the proposed simulation.

2.1 Objective

The objective function is minimizing the total operational costs while satisfying constraints related to DG capacity limits and fuel availability cost, optimal EV charging/discharging schedules, and DR load adjustments. It can be formulated as:

$$\text{Minimize} \left(\sum_{i=1}^{N_g} C_{DG}^i \left(P_{DG}^i(t) \right) + \sum_{j=1}^{N_d} C_{DR}^j \left(DR^j(t) \right) + \sum_{k=1}^{N_v} C_{V2G}^k \left(V2G^k(t) \right) \right) \quad (1)$$

Where N_g , N_d , and N_v are the number of DGs, DRs, and V2Gs, respectively. $P_{DG}^i(t)$ is the power output of the i^{th} DG unit, $DR^j(t)$ is the adjusted load from the j^{th} DR participant (i.e., the output of a DR), and $V2G^k(t)$ is the discharge output power from the k^{th} V2G. C_{DG}^i is DG fuel and maintenance cost, C_{V2G}^k is the k^{th} V2G unit operational cost in \$/kWh, and C_{DR}^j is DR cost which represents the incentive payments for response participants. Each one of costs is formulated in the next subsections.

Fig. 1. Flowchart of the proposed methodology

2.1.1 DG Cost

Total operational cost of a DG unit is calculated according to its amount produced power, it is formulated as shown in (2).

$$C_{DG}^i(P_{DG}^i(t)) = \alpha^i(P_{DG}^i(t))^2 + \beta^i(P_{DG}^i(t)) + \gamma^i S^i(t) + STC^i b^i(t) \quad \forall t \in T \text{ and } \forall i \in DG \quad (2)$$

where α^i , β^i , and γ^i are cost coefficients, T describes the set of hourly intervals, S^i is commitment flag $\in \{0,1\}$, STC^i is the startup cost and b^i is starting flag.

2.1.2 DR Cost

To participate effectively in the DR program, customers were required to provide basic information. Additionally, the program gathers necessary historical data depending on each customer's responsiveness. However, certain details are essential to calculate the DR costs. These include:

1. The maximum power reduction M^j (in megawatts) that customer j can sustain.
2. The period for which client j is existing to participate.
3. The annual participation frequency of customer j .

Based on the aforementioned data and the related parameters provided, the DR costs for a customer j can be formulated as shown in (3).

$$C_{Dr}^j \left(DR^j(t) \right) = \alpha^j \left(DR^j(t) \right)^2 + \beta^j \left(DR^j(t) \right) \quad \forall t \in T \text{ and } \forall j \in DRG \quad (3)$$

The primary objective is to determine the optimal virtual resource $DR(t)$ such that a predefined objective function is satisfied.

2.1.3 V2G Cost

V2G energy storage systems exhibit probabilistic behavior, as their operational mode whether acting as a load or a demand resource depends on the state of charge (SOC) of the EV battery. The DR cost associated with V2G systems is primarily determined by the operational costs of on-grid battery usage and can be mathematically expressed as follows:

$$C_{V2G}^k \left(V2G^k(t) \right) = \beta^k \left(V2G^k(t) \right) \quad \forall t \in T \text{ and } \forall k \in V2GR \quad (4)$$

Where $V2GR$ describes a set of resource units.

2.2 Constraints

The power balance constraint as explained in (5) ensures equilibrium between total generation and demand at each time interval t . Mathematically, the power balance is expressed as

$$\sum_{i=1}^{N_g} P_{DG}^i(t) + \sum_{j=1}^{N_d} DR^j(t) + \sum_{k=1}^{N_v} V2G^k(t) = \sum_{l=1}^{N_c} P_l^l(t), \quad \forall t \in T \quad (5)$$

Where $P_l^l(t)$ is the total demand of the l^{th} customer. N_c is the total number of customer loads. The voltage and current limitations for N buses are provided in (6) and (7) correspondingly.

$$V_{min} \leq V_i \leq V_{max} \quad \forall i \in N \quad (6)$$

$$I_i \leq I_{max} \quad \forall i \in N_{br} \quad (7)$$

Where N_{br} is a group of transmission branches. The power generation constraints for DGs are defined by (8), where G represents the total number of DGs.

$$P_{DG \ min}^i \leq P_{DG} \leq P_{DG \ max}^i \quad \forall i \in G. \quad (8)$$

For customer j , the DR constraints can be defined by (9), where DR_{max} denotes the maximum permissible reduction. Additionally, the bounds on DR prices can be specified by (10), with $P_d(t)$ representing the energy price at time t . P_H and P_L are the high/low electricity prices. The constraint related to the EV battery SOC limits is defined by (11).

$$DR_j \leq DR_{max} \quad (9)$$

$$P_H \leq P_d(t) \leq P_L \quad (10)$$

$$SOC_{EV \ min}^k \leq SOC_{EV} \leq SOC_{EV \ max}^k \quad (11)$$

3. Optimization Algorithms

This section presents novel metaheuristic optimization algorithms employed to address the optimal scheduling problem for Electric Vehicles (EVs) and Distributed Generation (DG) in smart grids with Demand Response (DR). Given the complexity of the problem, advanced metaheuristic optimization techniques, including Educational Competition Optimizer (ECO), Parrot Optimizer (PO), and Artemisinin Optimizer (AO) are used, to efficiently solve the high-dimensional, non-linear optimization challenge. These algorithms are selected due to their recent emergence, competitive performance in complex optimization problems, and adaptability to dynamic smart grid environments. All of those make these optimization algorithms suitable for EV-DG-DR scheduling.

The optimal scheduling of EVs, DG, and DR involves balancing cost, reliability, user comfort, and grid stability amid uncertainty, computational complexity, and infrastructure limitations. Specially, it is used for minimizing operational costs. Advanced techniques like metaheuristic optimizers (ECO, AO, PO), machine learning, and distributed control are being explored to overcome these challenges.

3.1 Educational Competition Optimizer

The ECO algorithm simulates competitive strategies across school levels, with optimization occurring in three progressive phases [47, 48]. General Steps of ECO are given in the following:

Initialization: ECO, initializes populations differently from other methods by using logical chaos mapping, which models social disorder due to educational deficiencies. In this study, the population size (N) and problem boundaries (Ub , Lb) are predefined. The mathematical formulation is presented next.

$$x_i = \alpha (x_{i-1}) (1 - x_{i-1}), 0 \leq x_o \leq 1, i = 1, 2, \dots, N, \alpha = 4. \quad (12)$$

Where x_i and x_{i-1} are the i^{th} and earlier values respectively, and α is a constant and the value of x_i given by:

$$X_i = Lb + (Ub - Lb) (x_i) \quad (13)$$

In the *Primary School Stage*: optimal locations can be determined based on the average distribution, while students compete to the nearest school. Update mechanisms for the school and the student populations are defined by:

$$School: X_i^{t+1} = X_i^t + \omega (X_{imean}^t - X_i^t). Levy(dim) \quad (14)$$

$$Students: X_i^{t+1} = X_i^t + \omega (close(X_i^t) - X_i^t). (randn) \quad (15)$$

$$\omega = 0.1 \ln \left(2 - \frac{t}{Max_{iter}} \right) \quad (16)$$

Where t and Max_{iter} refer to current and maximum iteration respectively. X_i^t is current position, X_i^{t+1} signifies the subsequent update position. The term X_{imean}^t denotes mean position of the vector corresponding to the i^{th} school in the t^{th} iteration round. *Levy(dim)* refers to the Lévy distribution applied in dimensional space as a random vector. The function *close*(X_i^t) returns the school nearest location to X_i^t , while *randn* is a normally distributed random variable.

In the Middle School Stage: As the number of schools decreases, they refined their locations according to the average population distribution and the most prominent positions. Students, in turn, set

personal academic goals influenced by nearby schools' proximity. As academic demands rise, student patience in learning is represented by P . Students are divided into academically gifted and non-gifted groups, with a threshold H of 0.5. Gifted students have a motivation level E , while non-gifted students have a fixed $E=1$. The parameter ω adjusts the learning step size. These behaviors are mathematically described by:

$$P = 4.randn. (1 - \frac{i}{Max_{iter}}) \tag{17}$$

$$E = \frac{\pi}{P} \cdot \frac{i}{Max_{iter}} \tag{18}$$

$$School: X_i^{t+1} = X_i^t + (X_{best}^t - X_{mean}^t) \cdot exp\left(\frac{i}{Max_{iter}} - 1\right) \cdot Levy(dim) \tag{19}$$

$$Students: X_i^{t+1} = \begin{cases} X_i^t - \omega \cdot close(X_i^t) - P \cdot (E \cdot \omega \cdot close(X_i^t) - X_i^t), R_1 < H \\ X_i^t - \omega \cdot close(X_i^t) - P \cdot (\omega \cdot close(X_i^t) - X_i^t), R_1 \geq H \end{cases} \tag{20}$$

The skill levels of various students are modeled by the random variable $R1$, which assumes a value between 0 and 1.

In the *High School Stage*: Schools employ a more precise evaluation, incorporating average, best, and worst populations positions to get their optimal location. Meanwhile, students target the top high school location. The optimization process drives students to compete for admission. Each iteration designates the fittest 10% as schools, with 90% remaining students. The dynamic behavior is mathematically described by (10) and (11).

$$School: X_i^{t+1} = X_i^t + (X_{best}^t - X_i^t) \cdot randn - (X_{best}^t - X_i^t) \cdot randn \tag{21}$$

$$Students: X_i^{t+1} = \begin{cases} X_{best}^t - P \cdot (E \cdot X_{best}^t - X_i^t), R_2 < H \\ X_{best}^t - P \cdot (X_{best}^t - X_i^t), R_2 \geq H \end{cases} \tag{22}$$

The abilities of individual students are depicted by a random number, R_2 , which ranges from 0 to 1.

The ECO algorithm persists in its search until a predefined stopping state is fulfilled. The overall structure of ECO is visually depicted in Fig. 2, offering a comprehensive guide to the optimization process, encompassing its iterative phases and search strategies.

Fig. 2. Flowchart of ECO algorithm

3.2 Parrot Optimizer (PO)

It is a novel metaheuristic algorithm that emulates how parrots explore their environment for food by using the following main stages foraging, staying, communications and fear of strangers ensuring a

balanced search mechanism. PO demonstrates superior convergence speed making it suitable for high-dimensional and multimodal problems [49]. General Steps of Parrot Optimizer are given in the following:

The proposed PO's initialization formula considers a swarm size of N , maximum iterations of Max_{iter} , and search space limits of lb (lower bound) and ub (upper bound), it can be represented.

$$x_i^0 = lb + rand(0,1) \cdot (ub - lb) \quad (23)$$

Where, $rand(0,1)$ represents a random number from 0 to 1, and x_i^0 represents i^{th} parrot position in the initial phase.

During foraging behavior in PO, they determine the approximate location of food mostly by watching the food's location as a result, the positional movement follows this equation:

$$x_i^{t+1} = (x_i^t - X_{best}) \cdot levy(dim) + rand(0.1) \left(1 - \frac{t}{max_{iter}}\right)^{\frac{2t}{max_{iter}}} \cdot x_{mean}^t \quad (24)$$

Where, X_i^t and X_{it+1} represent the current and the next update locations. The average location is represented by X_{mean}^t , while $Levy(D)$ represents the Levy distribution It describes how parrots fly. X_{best} denotes the best position. t is the current iteration. And X_{mean}^t , is calculated using:

$$X_{mean}^t = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=1}^N X_k^t \quad (25)$$

The staying behavior of the parrot consists of quickly flying to any vicinity of its owner's body. This process can be represented in the equation:

$$x_i^{t+1} = x_i^t + x_{best} \cdot Levy(dim) + rand(0,1) \cdot ones(1, dim) \quad (26)$$

where the all-1 vector of dimension, dim is indicated by $ones(1, dim)$. The flight to the host is shown by $X_{best} \cdot Levy(dim)$, and the procedure of randomly ending at host's body is indicated by $rand(0,1) \cdot ons(1, dim)$.

The social nature of parrots is demonstrated by their close communication within their groups. This procedure can be shown as follows:

$$x_i^{t+1} = \begin{cases} 0.2 \cdot rand(0.1) \cdot \left(1 - \frac{t}{max_{iter}}\right) \cdot (x_i^t - x_{mean}^t), & P \leq 0.5 \\ 0.2 \cdot rand(0.1) \cdot exp\left(\frac{-t}{rand(0.1) \cdot max_{iter}}\right), & P > 0.5 \end{cases} \quad (27)$$

Where $0.2 \cdot rand(0.1) \cdot \left(1 - \frac{t}{max_{iter}}\right) \cdot (x_i^t - x_{mean}^t)$ describes the process of an individual joining a group to communicate, and $0.2 \cdot rand(0.1) \cdot exp\left(\frac{-t}{rand(0.1) \cdot max_{iter}}\right)$ describes the process of an individual flying away shortly after communicating.

Parrots, like other birds, have an intrinsic fear of strangers. As mentioned in equation no (28)

$$x_i^{t+1} = X_i^t + rand(0.1) \cdot \cos\left(0.5\pi \cdot \frac{t}{max_{iter}}\right) \cdot (X_{best} - x_i^t) - \cos(rand(0.1) * \pi) \cdot \left(\frac{t}{max_{iter}}\right)^{\frac{2t}{max_{iter}}} \cdot (x_i^t - X_{best}) \quad (28)$$

Where $\cos(0.5\pi \cdot \frac{t}{max_iter}) \cdot (X_{best} - x_i^t)$ demonstrates the process of reorienting to fly towards the owner and $\cos(rand(0.1) * \pi) \cdot (\frac{t}{max_iter})^{\frac{2t}{max_iter}} \cdot (x_i^t - X_{best})$ demonstrates the act of moving away from strangers.

A detailed roadmap for the entire optimization process, including its iterative stages and search methods, is provided by the algorithm's full structure, which is depicted visually in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Flowchart of PO algorithm

3.3 Artemisinin Optimizer (AO)

AO algorithm draws inspiration from the therapeutic action of artemisinin in combating malaria, emulating the elimination of malaria parasites within the human body. The AO framework is built on three core strategies. Firstly, modeling the initial high-dosage phase of artemisinin treatment to rapidly reduce a significant portion of malaria parasites. Secondly, reflecting the progressive decrease in drug dosage during the middle to later treatment stages to clear residual malaria parasites. Thirdly, addressing the potential for malaria relapses in later treatment phases, a post-treatment consolidation strategy is incorporated. [50, 51].

Based on prior analysis, three unique strategies, inspired by different phases of artemisinin-based malaria treatment, have been developed. Their integration forms the core of the AO algorithm. General Steps of **AO** are given in the following equations:

This study models medicine microparticles as search agents in the AO algorithm, with their collective forming the solution set. The population, A , is initialized with N search agents across D dimensions, as defined in (29). This mimics drug breakdown and absorption, dispersing through the bloodstream to various body regions.

$$A_{N,D} = B + R \times (T - B) = \begin{bmatrix} a_{1,1} & a_{1,2} & \cdots & a_{1,D} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ a_{N,1} & a_{N,2} & \cdots & a_{N,D} \end{bmatrix} \quad (29)$$

T and B represent the space boundaries, and R represents random number sequences within $[0, 1]$. Like typical metaheuristic algorithms, AO uses these random sequences to initialize solutions.

In the first phase of malaria treatment, patients receive higher artemisinin doses to rapidly curb disease progression. The complex human body structure complicates drug distribution. This section presents a novel search model, described in (30), to simulate artemisinin diffusion.

$$\begin{cases} a_{i,j}^{t+1} = a_{i,j}^t + c \times a_{i,j}^t \times (-1)^t, r_1 < 0.5 \\ a_{i,j}^{t+1} = a_{i,j}^t + c \times best_j^t \times (-1)^t, r_1 > 0.5 \end{cases} \quad (30)$$

This strategy involves search agents that widely disperse to navigate the complex solution space, guided by random number $r_1 \in [0,1]$. Variables $a_{i,j}^{t+1}$ and $a_{i,j}^t$ denote the search agent's state post- and pre-update, respectively, with best as the current optimum. Drawing from pharmacokinetics, it models artemisinin diffusion, accounting for drug concentration decay over time. The parameter c represents the decay exponent of drug concentration in the human body.

as k acts as a probabilistic coefficient, reflecting the algorithm's evaluation progress to model varied patient responses and durations in this phase, The complete strategy for the elimination phase is then formulated by (31).

$$\begin{cases} a_{i,j}^{t+1} = a_{i,j}^t + c \times a_{i,j}^t \times (-1)^t, \text{ if } r_1 < 0.5 \text{ and } r_2 < k \\ a_{i,j}^{t+1} = a_{i,j}^t + c \times best_j^t \times (-1)^t, \text{ if } r_1 > 0.5 \text{ and } r_2 < k \end{cases} \quad (31)$$

Where r_2 is a random number within $[0, 1]$. After the initial treatment phase stabilizes the disease, the process shifts to the maintenance phase to achieve a full malaria cure.

The objective of second phase in malaria treatment aims to eradicate residual parasites after initial therapy. It uses lower artemisinin doses to prevent relapses and minimize side effects it can be calculated using Eq. (32) to determine the particle's position.

$$a_i^{t+1} = a_{b3}^t + d \times (a_{b1}^t - a_{b2}^t), \text{ if } r_3 < Fit_{norm}(i) \quad (32)$$

Where r_3 is a random number with values in $[0,1]$, $Fit_{norm}(i)$ represents the normalized fitness value, The coefficient b , ranging from $[0.1, 0.6]$.

In the third phase (post-consolidation phase) of AO algorithm simulates this scenario, modeling dormant parasites and unexpected relapses using Eq. (33) to account for persistent inactive forms in the body.

$$\begin{cases} a_{i,j}^{t+1} = a_{i,j}^t, \text{ if } r_4 < 0.05 \\ a_{i,j}^{t+1} = best_{i,j}, \text{ if } r_5 < 0.2 \end{cases} \quad (33)$$

Where r_4 and r_5 are random numbers in $[0,1]$, $best_{i,j}$ denotes a sub-vector of the current optimal solution in the j^{th} dimension. This equation models malaria parasites persisting in a dormant phase,

The algorithm metaphorically maps the human body as a constrained space, with parasites as candidate solutions and artemisinin as search agents. and Fig. 4 shows the flowchart of the operational structure for AO.

Fig. 4. Flow chart of the AO.

4. Case Study

The study was performed on transmission network IEEE 24-bus reliability test system and implemented to represent the transmission network. Fig. 5 describes a modified IEEE 24-bus system. It includes 11 Diesel Generator (DGs). Bus#13 is the swing bus. DR buses are 3, 4, 5, 8, 9, 10, 19, and 20. Among them, V2G units are proposed at buses 3 and 19 as shown in Fig. 5 with red circles. The peak demand is 2650.5MW at Hour 18.

Fig. 5. Modified IEEE 24-bus reliability test system

5. Simulation Results

To assess the effectiveness of the proposed scheduling approach, a detailed simulation study was conducted within the MATLAB platform. This section describes the simulation framework and delivers a comparative evaluation of the outcomes.

5.1 Optimizers Parameters

The simulation was structured to evaluate the performance of two test systems using algorithms: PSO, AO, PO, and ECO. The configuration parameters for each of these algorithms are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Parameters initialization of optimization algorithms.

Optimizers Parameters							
PSO		PO		ECO		AO	
Max iterations	1000	Max iterations	1000	Max iterations	1000	Max iterations	1000
Population size	50	Search agents	50	Search agents	50	Search agents	50
Weight damping ratio	0.99	Levy search, beta	1.5	Learning habit boundary, h	0.5		
Max/Min velocity Weight	0.7/0.3			proportion of primary school, g1	0.2		
Max/Min c1, c2	2.5/1.5			proportion of middle school, g2	0.1		

5.2 Results and comparative analysis

The proposed strategy was simulated and implemented to the transmission network IEEE 24-bus system in addition to the distribution network IEEE 33-bus system, and this section will discuss the results.

Simulation results of the proposed strategy in case of IEEE 24-bus system are presented in comparison tables (2, 3, 4, and 5) and figures (6 and 7). These tables and figures summarize the key results from the MATLAB simulation for optimum scheduling of DG, V2G, and DR. The tables include the best fitness values (cost) and elapsed times for each optimizer across the 24-hour period, as well as the average performance metrics.

From the results and comparison, the following are the important key findings. In case of time efficiency, ECO and AO consistently ran the fastest (~43–44s) but often sacrificed solution quality, and PO variants averaged ~87–89s, balancing speed and performance, while PSO was the slowest (~440–490s) due to its conventional iterative approach. In case of cost optimization, PO_F and PO achieved the lowest costs in 6/24 hours each. Additionally, the best trade-off, PO_F is recommended for most hours (best cost in 6 hours, fast runtime) and PSO is only viable if runtime is not a constraint.

Fig. 6. Best fitness (cost) across the 24-hour in IEEE 24-bus system

Table 2. Best fitness (cost) for each optimizer across the 24-hour in IEEE 24-bus system

Hour	Best fitness (Cost)							
	PSO (×1e4)	PO (×1e4)	PO_F (×1e4)	PO_S (×1e4)	PO_C (×1e4)	PO_O (×1e4)	ECO (×1e4)	AO (×1e4)
1	3.01	2.96	3.03	2.99	3.12	3.04	2.96	3.63
2	3.58	2.95	2.92	2.93	2.93	2.93	3.14	2.87
3	3.42	2.95	2.94	2.89	2.87	2.92	2.86	2.94
4	3.34	2.89	2.89	2.91	2.93	2.89	2.91	3.14
5	3.39	2.82	2.91	2.94	2.92	2.88	2.90	2.74
6	3.42	2.95	2.85	3.02	2.96	2.94	2.88	2.59
7	3.10	3.14	3.11	3.12	3.22	3.19	3.26	3.40
8	3.54	3.42	3.59	3.40	3.40	3.46	3.79	3.67
9	3.80	3.83	3.62	3.69	3.81	3.78	4.36	4.67
10	4.15	3.85	3.87	3.82	4.06	3.69	3.95	4.60
11	3.59	3.91	3.82	3.82	3.84	3.80	4.30	5.15
12	3.58	3.71	3.87	3.94	3.70	3.63	3.89	5.18
13	3.73	3.69	3.82	3.73	3.71	3.73	3.88	4.31
14	3.54	3.57	3.82	3.62	3.89	3.74	4.13	4.29
15	3.64	3.72	3.76	3.52	3.57	3.44	4.02	3.87
16	3.46	3.86	3.70	3.62	3.48	3.62	3.62	4.32
17	3.68	3.82	3.95	3.75	4.01	3.92	3.81	5.09
18	4.32	4.24	3.96	3.97	4.25	4.02	4.10	4.84
19	4.37	3.89	4.07	4.73	3.93	3.98	4.69	4.34
20	3.70	4.61	3.79	3.77	3.84	3.83	4.61	4.52
21	3.38	3.65	3.50	3.48	3.48	3.70	3.71	3.95
22	3.44	3.36	3.37	3.32	3.42	3.36	3.47	3.81
23	3.13	3.12	3.14	3.10	3.08	3.19	3.42	3.57
24	3.59	2.93	2.92	2.99	2.93	2.97	3.42	3.57

Table 3. Average Performance Metrics for each optimizer in IEEE 24-bus system

Metric	PSO	PO	PO_F	PO_S	PO_C	PO_O	ECO	AO
Average Cost (×1e4)	3.512	3.541	3.514	3.526	3.597	3.535	3.838	4.171
Average Time (s)	~450	~88	~88	~87	~88	~88	~44	~44

Table 4. Best Fitness and Elapsed Time at Hour = 18 in IEEE 24-bus system

Metric	PSO	PO	PO_F	PO_S	PO_C	PO_O	ECO	AO
Best Cost (×1e4)	4.3171	4.237	3.9591	3.9695	4.2493	4.0242	4.098	4.84
Elapsed Time (s)	444.89	87.26	87.665	87.193	87.329	89.682	43.75	43.63

Table 5. Optimal sizes of the units in IEEE 24-bus system at Hour = 18

Variable	PSO	PO	PO_F	PO_S	PO_C	PO_O	ECO	AO
DG_1	30.46	152.00	54.55	152.00	45.06	30.40	151.78	229.62
EV_1	46.51	0.04	50.00	1.87	19.41	50.00	49.83	38.00
DR_1	6.91	0.54	0.50	10.00	6.19	10.00	9.05	1.26
DR_2	3.74	8.00	0.50	8.00	1.21	0.70	0.50	1.02
DG_2	245.94	75.00	114.88	75.00	213.35	131.12	75.00	259.17
DR_3	1.42	0.54	0.96	1.92	1.79	0.50	2.30	3.79
DR_4	2.34	9.00	1.10	9.00	0.50	9.00	0.50	6.03
DR_5	3.73	0.54	4.50	9.00	2.27	1.19	9.00	1.16
DG_3	59.65	128.08	152.00	102.68	30.40	89.55	152.00	1.08
EV_2	29.32	60.00	60.00	60.00	36.59	17.54	27.48	59.70
DG_4	98.00	155.00	54.25	155.00	85.34	155.00	146.12	155.49
DG_5	153.13	155.00	155.00	155.00	154.99	155.00	155.00	119.49
DG_6	397.58	253.48	400.00	400.00	399.97	400.00	321.23	326.36
DR_6	35.69	47.34	0.88	50.00	50.00	0.00	50.00	133.90
DR_7	8.98	5.92	1.33	2.42	3.44	0.50	0.73	8.65
EV_3	388.65	400.00	400.00	400.00	399.97	400.00	400.00	254.20
DR_8	289.57	300.00	300.00	200.00	299.99	300.00	200.00	241.16
DG_7	258.83	310.00	310.00	268.62	309.99	310.00	310.00	220.42

Fig. 7. Convergence curve of the Best Fitness (Cost) in IEEE 24-bus system.

6. Conclusion and Future Recommendations

This study presented a comprehensive approach for the optimal sizing and scheduling of Distributed Generation (DG) and Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G) units integrated with Demand Response (DR) programs in smart grid environments. To address the complexities introduced by such integrations, three innovative metaheuristic optimization algorithms—Artemisinin Optimization (AO), Parrot Optimizer (PO), and Educational Competition Optimizer (ECO)—were employed and evaluated against the widely used Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) algorithm. The proposed framework effectively minimizes the total operational cost of the electrical distribution network while respecting all technical constraints associated with DGs, energy storage systems in EVs, and load demands. The strategy demonstrated strong adaptability and robustness in simulations conducted on transmission system (IEEE 24-bus). Results highlight that:

- The coordinated scheduling of DGs, V2G units, and DR enhances overall system efficiency.
- The novel optimizers (AO, PO, ECO) outperformed PSO in terms of cost savings and, in many cases, computational efficiency.
- The algorithms exhibited complementary strengths, while AO consistently achieved lower operational costs, ECO and some PO variants offered faster convergence in several scenarios.

These findings confirm that the integration of advanced optimizers in planning and operation can significantly enhance the performance of future smart grids by enabling cost-effective and sustainable energy management.

Building on the promising results of this research, several future directions are proposed to extend the current work:

- **Integration of Renewable Forecasting Uncertainties:** Incorporate stochastic modeling to account for the uncertainties associated with renewable energy generation (e.g., solar, wind), enhancing the reliability of the scheduling process.
- **Multi-Objective Optimization:** Explore multi-objective formulations that consider environmental impacts, user satisfaction, and grid stability alongside cost minimization.

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